

1. Introduction

An old say in French is “C’est dans les vieux pots que l’on fait la meilleure soupe” (i.e., best soups are made in old pots) and, in this contribution, we decided to try the old cuisine of mixing laws to tackle geometrical heterogeneities at mesoscale.

Analogous circuits in parallel and series are indeed very effective to obtain various equivalent properties (e.g., Renard and de Marsily, 1997). But **what about complex properties spectra** such as the frequency dependent electrical conductivity measured with Spectral Induced Polarization (SIP)?

3. Material and methods

Sample heterogeneous at mesoscopic scale

Heterogeneous samples made of montmorillonite and illite (studied by Mendieta et al., 2021) with a 10⁻² M NaCl solution: (a) well-mixed, (b) in serie, (c) and (d) in parallel with Illite on the top or montmorillonite on the top, respectively.

SIP measurements

Measurements with the SIP Fuchs III from 1 mHz to 20 kHz on (e) sample holder for SIP measurements (current injected between C1 and C2 and the potential measured in P1 and P2).

2. Mixing laws

	In parallel (Reuss, 1929)	$\sigma_R^* = \left(\frac{c}{\sigma_1^*} + \frac{1-c}{\sigma_2^*} \right)^{-1}$	σ^* complex conductivity of the material 1 (illite) and 2 (montmorillonite) c volumetric proportion of material 1 with respect to the whole volume ($c = 0.5$)
	In series (Voigt, 1910)	$\sigma_V^* = c\sigma_1^* + (1-c)\sigma_2^*$	
	Well mixed Self-consistent (Hashin, 1968)	$\sigma_{SC}^* = \sigma_2^* + \frac{3c\sigma_2^*}{3\sigma_2^* + (1-c)(\sigma_1^* - \sigma_2^*)}(\sigma_1^* - \sigma_2^*)$	

SIP results

Measured complex conductivity spectra (symbols) compare favourably to three classical mixing laws (solid lines): the so-called Wiener bounds, i.e., the model in parallel (Reuss, 1929) and the model in series (Voigt, 1910), and the self-consistent approach proposed by Hashin (1968).

5. Conclusions & Discussion

Our results clearly show that mixing laws compare really well with our experimental spectra (for the real and imaginary part). The only unexpected exception is for the sample in parallel with the illite placed on top (light blue line). This could be explained by the potential electrodes location.

This work showed that the mixing laws are effective to provide equivalent spectra of complex conductivity for heterogeneous media.

Since many natural media are organized in layers, this opens up a way to improve or simplify IP modelling for various applications from reservoir properties to Critical Zone studies.

References

Hashin, Z. (1968). Assessment of the self consistent scheme approximation: conductivity of particulate composites, *J. Composite Mater.*, 2(3), 284–300.
 Jougnot, D. (2020). Developing hydrogeophysics for critical zone studies, importance of heterogeneities and processes at the mesoscopic scale. HDR dissertation. Sorbonne Université, Paris.
 Mendieta, A., Jougnot, D., Leroy, P., & Mainault, A. (2021). Spectral induced polarization characterization of non-consolidated clays for varying salinities—An experimental study. *J. Geophys. Res.: Solid Earth*, 126(4), e2020JB021125.
 Mendieta, A., Mainault, A., Leroy, P., & Jougnot, D. (2023). Spectral induced polarization of heterogeneous non-consolidated clays. *Geophys J. Int.*, 233(1), 436–447.
 Naylor, L. A., Zheng, Y., Munro, N., Stanton, A., Wang, W., Chng, N. R., ... & Waldron, S. (2023). Bringing Social Science Into Critical Zone Science: Exploring Smallholder Farmers' Learning Preferences in Chinese Human-Modified Critical Zones. *Earth's Future*, 11(9), e2022EF003472.
 Renard, P., & De Marsily, G. (1997). Calculating equivalent permeability: a review. *Adv. Water Resour.*, 20(5–6), 253–278.
 Reuss, A. (1929). Berechnung der Fließgrenze von Mischkristallen auf Grund der Plastizitätsbedingung für Einkristalle, *Zeitschrift für Angew. Math. Mech.*, 9(1), 49–58.
 Voigt, W., (1910). *Lehrbuch der Kristallphysik*, Teubner-Verlag, Leipzig, Germany.

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